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Ikechukwu, Elizabeth Chinenye, Michael Uchendu Agunannah,
Dr. Kingson Nduagwuik Njoku & S. U. Nwibo

Agro-Terrorism Acts and Farmers Awareness in Ebonyi State

¹Ikechukwu, Elizabeth Chinenye, ²Michael Uchendu Agunannah, ³Dr. Kingson Nduagwuik Njoku, ⁴S. U. Nwibo

^{1&4}Agricultural Extension and Management Department, Ebonyi State University, Abakiliki.

²Agricultural Technology Department, Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana, Afikpo

³Department of Criminal Justice Administration & Emergency Management, Colorado State University, Global Aurora, USA.

¹ikechukwuchinenye@gmail.com, ²agumike2016@gmail.com, ³drkinggf@yahoo.com

¹08061111072, ²08068378058, ³+17048063458, ⁴070332107110

Abstract

This paper presents a survey on agro-terrorism awareness conducted in Ebonyi State, focusing on farmers' understanding of the concept and their preparedness to combat existing threats and prevent future occurrences of agro-terrorism. The study utilized a multi-stage random sampling technique to select respondents, with two Local Government Areas (LGAs) chosen randomly from each of the three agricultural zones in Ebonyi State. From each selected L.G.A., twenty farmers were randomly sampled from each of the twelve communities, resulting in a total sample size of 240 farmers. Data for the study were collected through structured questionnaires and interview schedules, and descriptive statistics was employed for data analysis. The results indicate that 91.7% of respondents are aware of herdsmen's attacks, while 69.2% indicated their awareness of crop infestation. Additionally, awareness of livestock poisoning, water poisoning, and coercing farmers to buy genetically modified seeds (GMO) were reported at 56.7%, 44.6%, and 14.6%, respectively. Based on the findings, the study recommends the implementation of adequate public sensitization campaigns to raise awareness about agro-terrorism and its potentially serious consequences.

Keywords: Agro-Terrorism, Farmers', Awareness, Ebonyi State, Preparedness

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1.0 Introduction

Agro-terrorism can be described as the deliberate act of disrupting the production and distribution of agricultural products through the use of biological agents. Additionally, it involves targeting farmers by groups such as the Fulani herdsmen, with the aim of instilling fear and creating terror. This is achieved by employing threats related to food or water security to manipulate the target audience, who may become subjects of terror, demands, or heightened attention, depending on whether the primary objective is coercion, propaganda, or intimidation (Parker, 2002). Agro-terrorism is also the intentional introduction of a plant virus, pathogen, or other biological agents to destroy animals or crops and poisoning of farmers' ponds (Stack, Suffert, and Gullino, 2010; Monke, 2004).

According to Njiruh and Wakhungu (2017), the agricultural sector presents numerous vulnerability points to potential attacks, making it highly susceptible to disruptions within any country's economy. Consequently, such disruptions can have severe and far-reaching repercussions. Any interference at various stages of the food chain has the potential to trigger food insecurity, national instability, as well as direct and indirect economic ramifications, particularly in nations where agriculture plays a significant role in their gross domestic product (GDP) (Gary, 2016). Ebonyi State is a Southeastern state in Nigeria, which was established in 1991. The state has a population of over 2,504,100 people, with a majority of them being farmers; both subsistent and commercial. The state government has invested in several agro-based initiatives, including the Abakiliki rice mill, Abakiliki Fertilizer farm, and Osu-Edda rice mill, among others (National Bureau of Statistics, NBS, 2017). The state has two distinct seasons; the rainy season which runs from April to early November and the dry season which lasts from late November to early April. The FADAMA areas, which are large lowland regions, are ideal for rice cultivation during the dry season and vegetable farming (Ekpe, Okorie, Ogbodo & Nwite, 2005).

In addition to farming, there are a variety of non-farm activities that take place in the state. These include petty trading, pottery, blacksmithing, and weaving. The state is also home to several industries, including a fertilizer blending plant, quarry factories, and one of Nigeria's largest poultry companies, Nkali Poultry.

Furthermore, the state boasts one of Nigeria's top cement industries, the Nigerian Cement Company at Nkalagu. Abakaliki is also known for its rice milling

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industries and building materials industry (Ebonyi State Ministry of Information, EBMOI, 2005).

On the basis of Gary's (2016) findings on using the knowledge of agro-terrorism as part of a preparedness strategy in combating disease outbreaks, this study aims at unveiling the Ebonyi State farmers' level of awareness of agro-terrorism. It utilized primary data collected through structured questionnaires from 240 respondents across 6 local governments in Ebonyi. Findings from the study will aid farmers in the state, the government of the state, and other related agencies to improve their bio-security measures and enhance surveillance and restriction in and around farm facilities as well as securing the livelihood of the majority of the population.

Figure 1: Map of Ebonyi State (Source : EBMOI, 2005)

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2.0 Literature Review

Agricultural commodities find their way onto dining tables as sustenance, or onto retail shelves in the form of therapeutic agents. Opposition to this process would significantly impede the progress of the food, pharmaceutical, and medical sectors. Specifically in 2006, amidst the avian influenza outbreak in Nigeria's Northern Province, the virus propagated across all agro-ecological regions within the country leading to the death of nearly 1.2 million domesticated avian species. This outcome stemmed from inadequate disease control practices adopted by farmers (Njiruh & Wakhungu, 2017). Furthermore, in the year 1984, approximately 45 individuals required hospitalization following an incident involving a Rajneeshee group. This cult contaminated ten salad bars located in Dallas, Oregon with the salmonella bacterium (Kenneth, 2011).

Agro-terrorism can take numerous forms, including livestock poisoning and the intentional introduction and spread of plant and animal infections. Agro-terrorism is carried out in a variety of ways, including the spread of infections in the fields by competitors, the transfer of plant and animal material during competitions, and the importation of food and seed (Pimentel, Lach, Zuniga & Morrison, 2000). In a study conducted by Kenneth (2011), it was highlighted that the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) voiced apprehensions regarding the potential threats of food terrorism and inadvertent food contamination incidents leading to severe instances of foodborne illnesses with widespread impact. The study further emphasized the interconnectedness of these concerns with regard to both imported food products and food-related materials. Recent developments have underscored the validity of these concerns, with documented cases of foodborne illnesses and contamination stemming from imported food items on a global scale. This is particularly noticeable in countries facing challenges in ensuring food safety standards.

So many people in the world are at risk of unsafe food which leads to sickness and death. The food chain starts from farm to fork/plate. Terrorism intended against our food plants and animals poses a range of risks, including the amount of death, economic damage, and a loss of moral and consumer confidence. Both the export and import markets for food and agricultural products will be harmed (Benjamin, Calum & William, 2005).

The US Department of Agriculture stated in 1985 that Mexican contract employees were spreading screwworm (*cochliomyia hominivorax*) among animals on

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purpose. The world's population depends on agro-products for their food. If infected food reaches the dining room or if an animal pathogen is transmissible to people, human health may be endangered (zoonotic). The 2015 poisoning of wells and streams in the Northeastern part of Nigeria by the Islamic group, Boko Haram, is a typical example (Chukwuma, 2016).

Similarly, unauthorized encroachment into farmlands leading to serious and deadly conflicts between farmers and herdsmen in several parts of Nigeria in recent times also constitutes some form of agro-terrorism. In this case, herdsmen's cows stray into farmers' farmland without permission and thereby damage crops and fallow lands that are left to replenish. It is also an undeniable fact that the Fulani herdsmen's attacks on farmers have resulted in a significant economic setback in Nigeria. Food scarcity, inflation and devaluation of the naira, decreased output per capita, discouragement in farm/crop investments, and the generation of refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs) are among its consequences (Ndubuisi, 2018).

According to Ferguson, Donnelly, and Anderson (2001), agriculture has in the past years been prone to agro-terrorism because crops are cultivated over large areas that are poorly monitored; crops are thus vulnerable and there is relatively little chance to identify a perpetrator or the date that a biological pathogen was introduced in an area. Consequently, it may be present for months before it is identified.

Some of the causes of agro-terrorism as identified by Ferguson et al. (2001), Abadie (2004) and Yusuf (2010) include the existence of glaring political inequalities where agro-terrorism is used to channel grievances; enforcement or coercing of farmers and the government into adopting of Genetically Modified (GMO) seeds which cannot be replicated; poisoning of export products by competitions amongst countries leading to trade restrictions on rival country; and the deprivation of enemy countries' food supply leading to famine like the case of brown spot disease of rice which contributed to the Bengal famine in India between 1942 and 1943.

3.0 Methodology

The research utilized a multi-stage random sampling method to select participants for the study. This approach was chosen for its effectiveness in efficiently surveying extensive population clusters, thereby ensuring a well-distributed representation of data across the entire population. This method enhances the study's ability to capture diverse perspectives and characteristics within the target population.

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Stage one: Random selection of two Local Government Areas (L.G.As) from the three agricultural zones in Ebonyi State is conducted. Consequently, cumulative of six (6) L.G.As were being encompassed within the State for the purpose of this study. In this context, the research intends to strategically select two LGAs from each of the three agricultural zones in Ebonyi State, thereby achieving a comprehensive representation of the state's diverse agricultural regions. This approach is aimed at ensuring a robust and holistic understanding of the agricultural landscape, allowing for distinct insights and well-informed conclusions. By incorporating a total of six LGAs, this study seeks to attain a comprehensive overview of the agricultural dynamics within Ebonyi State, facilitating more accurate and applicable recommendations for policy and practice

Stage two: From the six Local Government Areas that were randomly selected, two communities were randomly selected. This gave a total of twelve (12) communities in the state.

Stage three: Specifically, twenty farmers were randomly chosen from each of the twelve communities within the State, resulting in a cumulative sample size of two hundred and forty participants. This approach ensures a comprehensive and diverse dataset, enhancing the study's validity and ability to generalize findings across the population of interest.

Data for the study were primarily collected using structured questionnaires and interview schedules. In the research study, surveys were distributed to participants with proficient reading and writing skills, while one-on-one interviews were conducted with participants who lacked the ability to read and write. The received answers were documented in alignment with their respective communication methods. The data-gathering tool was methodically structured into distinct sections that corresponded to the precise goals of the investigation. This meticulous organization facilitated the systematic collection of data in line with the study's defined objectives.

Data collected on agro-terrorism acts included acts of terrorism such as herdsmen attacks, water poisoning, livestock poisoning, and crop infestation, and the farmer's awareness was scaled in, aware and not aware.

Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages, etc. were employed to identify the agro-terrorism knowledge level of farmers in Ebonyi State.

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4.0 Results

The different agro-terrorism acts and farmer's awareness in the area were assessed in this section and the result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Agro-terrorism Acts and Farmers' Awareness

Agro-terrorism Acts	Frequency (n=240)	Percentage	Awareness	Decision
Herdsmen attack(on crops /farmers)	220	91.7	3.8	Accept
Water poisoning	107	44.6	2.2	Reject
Livestock poisoning	136	56.7	2.7	Accept
Crop infestation	166	69.2	3.1	Accept
Coercing farmers to buy genetically modified seeds (GMO)	35	14.6	2.4	Reject

(Source: Field Survey, 2019)

The outcomes presented in Table 1 elucidate the extent to which respondents possess knowledge regarding various agro-terrorism incidents. The collected responses indicate a noteworthy trend, wherein the majority of participants (91.7%) demonstrate familiarity with the herdsmen attack in Ebonyi State. Subsequently, 69.2% of respondents acknowledge their awareness of the occurrence of crop infestation in the same State. Moreover, a significant proportion of participants, constituting 44.6%, 56.7%, and 14.6% respectively, exhibit awareness concerning incidents involving water poisoning, livestock poisoning, and the coerced adoption of genetically modified seeds among farmers.

An in-depth examination of farmers' awareness levels pertaining to agro-terrorism phenomena unveils that herdsmen attacks (mean score: 3.8), livestock poisoning (mean score: 2.7), and crop infestation (mean score: 3.1) have garnered considerable acknowledgment. Conversely, the recognition of incidents such as water poisoning and the coerced adoption of genetically modified seeds by farmers is relatively inadequate. This deficiency in awareness is reflected in their comparatively lower mean scores, signifying limited comprehension of these aspects.

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5.0 Discussion

The study's findings reveal that a significant portion (91.7%) of the participants possesses an awareness of incidents involving attacks by herdsmen, with 69.2% confirming occurrences of crop infestation. Additionally, 56.7%, 44.6%, and 14.6% respectively indicated their recognition of instances related to livestock poisoning, water contamination, and coercive promotion of genetically modified seeds (GMOs). The outcome of this investigation underscores the prominence of herdsmen attacks as the foremost form of agro-terrorism in Ebonyi State. This distressing reality has contributed to the loss of both human lives and property, resulting in considerable adversity for local farmers. To address these issues, it is imperative for the government to establish comprehensive policies and regulations that effectively deter unauthorized encroachments onto agricultural properties, thereby mitigating crop destruction and harm to farmers. Also, the application of robust biosecurity measures is essential to curbing incidents of livestock and water contamination, which in turn have significant implications for the region's economic well-being.

6.0 Conclusion

The study assessed the farm-level knowledge of agro-terrorism in Ebonyi state, Nigeria. Primary data was sourced with the aid of a well-structured questionnaire and analysed using appropriate statistical tools. Questionnaires were used to collect the data for the study from a sample of 240 respondents using multi-staged sampling techniques. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics in accordance with the study objectives. The findings from this study revealed that agro-terrorism like herdsmen attacks and crop infestation ranked high among the agro-terrorism acts and farmers' awareness in the study area with their respective 91.7% and 69.2% affirmation from the correspondents while livestock poisoning, water poisoning, and coercing farmers to buy genetically modified seeds (GMO) received 56.7%, 44.6%, and 14.6% awareness.

7.0 Recommendations

The findings underline the varying degrees of awareness among farmers regarding different agro-terrorism incidents. While some incidents have been widely acknowledged, others remain insufficiently recognized. This nuanced awareness distribution highlights the need for targeted educational and awareness-raising

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initiatives within the agricultural community to address gaps in understanding surrounding agro-terrorism-related issues. To this end, the following under-listed recommendations are made:

- i. There should be public awareness and outreach programmes on the issue of agro-terrorism among farmers in the State.
- ii. Early detection and rapid response to agro-terrorism depend on close cooperation between farmers, health authorities, and law enforcement. National detection assets and vaccines should be made available for farmers to have access to them.
- iii. Government should enact policies to curb the menace of herdsmen's attacks on farmers.

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